

MICROSTRUCTURE, PHASE TRANSFORMATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF NiMnGa/Sn COMPOSITES

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Abstract. This paper proposes to prepare NiMnGa/Sn composites by compositing NiMnGa particles and Sn powder. The microstructure, martensitic transformation and mechanical properties of the bulk alloy, ball-milled powders and composites were systematically investigated. The results show that the milled NiMnGa particles are mainly flaky in shape, and the alloy transforms from ordered to disordered structure after ball milling. The martensitic transformation of milled NiMnGa particles disappeared and it is recovered by post-annealing. The annealed NiMnGa particles and Sn powder were mixed and sintered to make NiMnGa particles /Sn composites. The composites exhibit a different NiMnGa particle distribution morphology for the axial direction and radial direction of the sample. The interfacial reaction between the NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix is observed. The martensitic transformation of the 30% and 40% composites has been observed, but the transformation temperatures for the composites are higher than that of the annealed NiMnGa particles, which should be related to the interfacial reaction that changes the composition of the NiMnGa particles. Most of the composites are not fractured during compressive test irrespective of the particles distribution and show a large plasticity, the mechanical strength of the composites increases with increasing the NiMnGa particle content.

Keywords: NiMnGa, Composite materials, Microstructure, Martensitic transformation, Mechanical properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy transducers commonly have two basic modes of operation, one in which an active material vibrates under an applied excitation to produce sound waves, and the other in which the active material converts the received vibrations into electromagnetic signals[1]. Typical transducer materials include piezoelectric ceramics, magnetostrictive materials, and their composite materials[2-5]. NiMnGa alloy is a magnetic shape memory alloy (FSMA) with large magnetic-field induced strain (MFIS) and high response frequency[6,7], which demonstrates great potential for applications in the domain of sensor and transducers[8]. However, NiMnGa alloy belongs to intermetallic compounds, and the brittleness is large that is not conducive to application[9]. Preparing porous alloys or particles and then compositing them with ductile matrix to form composites is an effective way to enhance the mechanical properties of NiMnGa alloys[10-12]. The two main types of common matrices are polymers and metals. However, the ageing of polymers leads to the deterioration of the mechanical properties of composites, which limits their application to a certain extent. Moreover, the interfacial bonding between the polymer matrix and NiMnGa particles is weak, which is not beneficial for stress transfer under mechanical loading. Metal matrix, on the other hand, can be a good solution to the above problems. Metal matrix composites have better interfacial bonding strength and higher mechanical strength, and show more stable physicochemical characteristics under specific conditions. The preparation of NiMnGa composites using Mg, Cu, and Al metals as the matrix has been reported, and the composites exhibit higher strength and ductility compared to a single metal matrix or NiMnGa alloy, indicating that compositing NiMnGa alloys with ductile metal matrix is an effective way to improve its property[11,13-15].

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Metal Sn has large plasticity and ductility, but poor strength, the compositing of NiMnGa particles and Sn may be an effective way to solve the brittleness of NiMnGa alloy and improve the strength of Sn matrix at the same time. In this article, NiMnGa alloy particles were firstly prepared by ball milling method, and then the NiMnGa/Sn composites were prepared by powder metallurgy method. The microstructure, phase transformation, and mechanical properties of the composites were systematically investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Ni_{40.8}Mn_{38.1}Ga_{21.1} ferromagnetic shape memory alloy ingot was prepared by arc-melting of high purity elements of Ni, Mn and Ga under an argon atmosphere. The alloy was melted by rotating the melt 6 times, and the magnetic stirring was applied after the 2nd rotation to ensure homogeneity of the alloy composition. Then the as-cast ingot was homogenized in argon atmosphere at 1123 K for 9 h followed by water-quenching. The NiMnGa alloy powder was prepared by ball milling and post annealing at 1023 K for 2 h. The ball milling was performed using a QM-3A ball mill with hardened steel balls and ball-to-powder ratio was 8:1, ball milling time was 15 min, 25 min and 35 min. Alcohol was added as ball milling medium to reduce the occurrence of cold-welding, and cool the ball milling tank to avoid overheating. Using QM-3A ball mill to mix the annealed 35 min-milled NiMnGa alloy powder and Sn powder for 20 min without milling balls, and the NiMnGa powder weight ratio was chosen as 20%, 30% and 40%. The mixed powder was transferred into the mould and then cold-pressed, and finally the pressed samples were sintered at 428K for 1h under an argon atmosphere to obtain NiMnGa/Sn composites. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the preparation of NiMnGa/Sn composites.

The microstructure of the samples was characterized using a FEI Apreo-C scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyzer. Phase constitution was identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Panalytical X-pert PRO diffractometer with Cu K_α radiation at room temperature. Martensitic transformation of the samples was investigated using a Pekin-Elmer Diamond differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). The compression tests were carried out using an Instron universal testing machine (Model 3365) at a deformation speed of 0.5 mm/min. The size of the compression testing samples was ~Φ3 mm × 6 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the preparation of NiMnGa/Sn composites.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

Figure 2 shows SEM images of NiMnGa particles prepared by different ball milling time. Figure 2 (a), (b) and (c) corresponds to ball milling time of 15 min, 25 min and 35 min, respectively. It can be seen that all the NiMnGa particles are flaky in shape, and the size of particles seems to be decreased gradually as the milling time increases. The 35 min ball milled NiMnGa particles have many fine particles and show a wider size distribution.

Figure 2: SEM images of NiMnGa powder with different ball milling time, (a) 15 min, (b) 25min, and (c) 35min

The XRD patterns of Figure 3 show that the structural evolution from NiMnGa ingots to powder with the milling time. At room temperature, the diffraction peaks of NiMnGa alloy can be mainly indexed as body-centered tetragonal structure martensite phase (peaks corresponding to the black dashed line), indicating that the bulk NiMnGa alloy is a single martensite phase at room temperature. After 15 min ball milling, the structure of the powder turns into a disordered cubic structure (peaks corresponding to the yellow dashed line). With the increase of ball milling time, the diffraction peaks of the disordered cubic phase structure seem to be enhanced gradually. And for the XRD pattern of the 35 min sample, only the diffraction peaks of the disordered cubic structure exist which agrees with the results of cryo-milling Ni_{49.4}Mn_{30.3}Ga_{20.3} powders[16]. This indicates that the structure of the alloy was destroyed during the ball milling process, and evolved from ordered to disordered. Correspondingly the martensitic transformation should be also affected, which was verified in the subsequent DSC analysis, and the phase transformation did not occur in the ball milled powder during both heating and cooling cycles.

Figure 3: Room-temperature XRD patterns of NiMnGa bulk alloy and powders with different ball milling time.

To recover the ordered structure and martensitic transformation of ball-milled NiMnGa particles, the milled particles are annealed at 1023 K for 1 h. Then the annealed 35 min-milled particles were composited with Sn powder. The SEM micrographs of the annealed NiMnGa particle and the Sn powder have been shown in Figure 4(a) and (b), respectively. It can be seen that the Sn powder exhibits irregularly spherical or dumbbell shape that is different from the flaky NiMnGa particles, which should be beneficial for the densification of the composites under compression with different shape raw powders. Figure 4(c), (e) and (g) shows SEM images of the composites taken at the axial direction of the sample, Figure 4(d), (f) and (h) shows SEM images of the composites taken at the radial direction of the sample, and Figure 4(i) shows the schematic diagram of different directions. It can be seen that the darker black phase is the NiMnGa alloy particles and the lighter grey phase should be the Sn matrix.

From the SEM image of 20% composite, it can be found that along the axial direction the NiMnGa alloy particles are widely dispersed in the light grey Sn matrix. Along the radial direction, the large-size NiMnGa alloy particles present a sheet-like structure, uniformly distributed in the matrix. This special particle morphology is not only related to the shape of the original ball-milled particles, but also may be related to the cold-pressing effect on the sample, in which the alloy particles are redistributed due to the applied compression stress during the cold-pressing process. As the NiMnGa particle content increases, the particle dispersion uniformity decreases. The distribution of particles is relatively homogeneous in the composites with 20% particle content, whereas in the composites with 40% particle content the local agglomeration of NiMnGa particles occurs.

Figure 4: SEM images of (a) NiMnGa particles, (b) Sn powder, (c) 20% composite axial, (d) 20% composite radial, (e) 30% composite axial, (f) 30% composite radial, (g) 40% composite axial, (h) 40% composite radial, (i) schematic diagrams of different directions.

The EDS test results on the surface of 40% composite are given in Figure 5(a), clearly indicating the distribution of NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix in the sample, which is consistent with the above analysis result in Figure 4. Figure 5(b) further shows the line-scan EDS results across the interface of the NiMnGa particle and Sn matrix. The high magnification SEM image shows that the interface between the NiMnGa particles and Sn matrix under the combined effect of cold pressing and sintering is relatively tight, and the irregular surface of the particles is conducive to the mechanical bonding between the matrix and the particles, but some irregularly shaped holes at the interface are also observed. The line-scan EDS result shows a wide Ni, Mn, Ga and Sn elements distribution on the interface, indicating a slight chemical reaction at the interface happens. For Sn alloys, elemental diffusion may lead to the formation of Kirkendall holes, and the irregular microporosity near the interface may be the Kirkendall holes caused by elemental diffusion [17]. Therefore, the holes at the interfacial area could be related to the Kirkendall effect due to the mutual elemental diffusion. In addition, the holes away from the interface show a more regular round shape, which may be related to the introduced gas pores during the cold-compression process.

Figure 6 shows the XRD patterns of NiMnGa/Sn composites with different particle contents. The black squares, blue circles and green triangles labelled on the pattern correspond to the diffraction peaks of NiMnGa particles, NiSn compound and Sn, respectively. It can be seen that, with the increase of NiMnGa content, the intensity of NiMnGa diffraction peaks gradually increases. The diffraction peaks at $\sim 28^\circ$ and $\sim 73^\circ$ are the diffraction peaks of NiSn, indicating the existence of new compound that should be caused by the interfacial reaction between Sn matrix and NiMnGa particles, which are in agreement with the EDS result shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: (a) EDS result of elemental distribution of NiMnGa/Sn composites, (b) line-scan EDS result of elemental distribution at the interface.

Figure 6: Room-temperature XRD patterns of the annealed NiMnGa powder and NiMnGa/Sn composite.

3.2 Phase transformation

Figure 7: The DSC curves of (a) annealed NiMnGa particles, (b) 20% composite, (c) 30% composite and (d) 40% composite.

Figure 7 shows the DSC curves of annealed NiMnGa particles and NiMnGa/Sn composites. It can be seen that the annealed NiMnGa particles exhibit a clear martensitic transformation during heating/cooling process. However, the composite with 20% particle content has no significant phase transformation peaks observed, which should result from the low content of NiMnGa particles. With further content increase of NiMnGa particles, phase transformation peaks are observed in 30% and 40% of the composites. The A_s and M_f of annealed NiMnGa particles are 100.1 °C and 86.9 °C, respectively. The A_s and M_f temperatures of the composite with 30% NiMnGa content are 144.8 °C and 117.4 °C, and those of 40% NiMnGa content are 159.1 °C and 130.1 °C, respectively. It can be seen that the phase transformation temperature of the composite is higher than that of the annealed NiMnGa particles, and with the increase of NiMnGa particle content, the phase transformation temperature of the composites also increases. The change in phase transformation temperature may be related to the interfacial reaction between the matrix and the particles, which altered the composition of the NiMnGa particles to some extent.

3.3 Mechanical properties of composites

In order to investigate the effect of NiMnGa particle distribution and content on the mechanical properties of the composites, different specimens were cut along the axial and radial directions of the composite samples for compression experiments. Figure 8(a) shows the stress-strain curve along the axial compression. It can be seen that, except for the NiMnGa/Sn composites with 40% particle content, all the composites show significant plastic deformation behavior, and are not completely fractured when the compressive strain reaches 80%. Figure 8(b) shows the compressive stress-strain curve of the specimen cut along the radial direction. It can be seen that the deformation stage is basically similar to the axial specimen, all the samples are not completely fractured and the samples are compressed to a thin sheet finally. Besides, different from compressive curve along axial direction, the stress-strain curve along the radial compression shows a minor fluctuation during loading, which could be correlated to the different NiMnGa particles distribution in different directions shown in Figure 4. Overall, the compressive strength of composites increases with

increasing the NiMnGa particle content, which mainly result from the reinforcing effect of the NiMnGa particles.

Figure 8: Compressive stress-strain curves of composite materials, (a) axial compression, (b) radial compression

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have successfully prepared NiMnGa/Sn composites by ball milling and sintering method. NiMnGa particles prepared by ball milling are flaky-shape. After ball milling, the ordered structure of the alloy is destroyed and the martensitic transformation correspondingly disappears. The martensitic transformation of the NiMnGa particles is retrieved after post-annealing. The NiMnGa alloy particles are widely dispersed in the Sn matrix, and exhibit a different distribution morphology at axial and radial direction of the samples. The interfacial bonding between the NiMnGa particles and the Sn matrix is relatively tight mainly correlated to the interfacial reaction. In the composite with 20% NiMnGa particles, the martensitic transformation is not observed due to the low content of NiMnGa particles. The 30% and 40% composites exhibit martensitic transformation but with higher transformation temperatures than that of the original annealed NiMnGa particles. With the increase of NiMnGa particle content, the compressive strength of the composite increases. Most of the composites demonstrate a large plasticity without completely fracturing during compression.

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